

ESSAY

Cost-benefit analysis of the offshore wind power transition in the Mediterranean: Towards a “New Eldorado”?

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Abstract

The condition of the environment remains at the forefront of contemporary debates among political leaders and societal stakeholders, particularly in the context of addressing climate change. Offshore Wind Farms (OWFs) are emerging as a promising pathway for renewable energy development in the Mediterranean. While existing literature extensively explores the potential of OWF technology in advancing climate neutrality targets by 2030, comparatively little attention has been given to the challenges and trade-offs associated with its implementation. This essay examines the costs and benefits of deploying OWFs in the Mediterranean, assessing their economic, environmental, and social impacts through a trade-off analysis. Despite regulatory and environmental challenges, the deployment of OWFs in the Mediterranean is set to expand, driven by low marginal costs, favourable climatic and geographic conditions, and growing interest from international investors. The study underscores the urgent need for comprehensive legislation to address environmental, social, and economic risks, critically evaluating gaps in the current legal framework and examining the opportunities and challenges associated with renewable energy expansion. The analysis serves as a valuable resource for policymakers, investors, and environmental advocates, providing a framework to balance environmental preservation with the expansion of renewable energy. Addressing these critical considerations aims to support the creation of strategies that foster a harmonious integration of renewable energy projects within the Mediterranean region’s environmental and socio-economic landscape.

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

Mediterranean Sea, Green Deal, Barcelona Convention, Offshore Wind Energy, Floating Technology

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Introduction

As the global energy transition becomes increasingly critical, debates and studies on renewable energies are gaining renewed attention. Seas and oceans act as vast energy collectors, primarily through solar energy, which can be converted into potential, kinetic, and thermal energy. The Mediterranean Sea, capturing substantial solar energy and generating water currents, offers opportunities for energy production via submerged turbines, transforming renewable and inexhaustible energy into electricity. Wind energy dominates the Mediterranean's renewable potential, especially with floating wind turbine technology advancements. However, despite existing measures in place, Europe's natural environment is degrading rapidly, and it necessitates constant legislative updates to align urban and industrial growth with environmental sustainability¹. In this respect, sustainable development focuses on fulfilling current needs while ensuring future generations can satisfy theirs². It requires economic efficiency, social equity, and environmental sustainability while integrating ecological concerns with societal and financial priorities³. Renewable energy derives from inexhaustible and continuously replenished sources, and it offers a crucial response to the climate crisis. In the Mediterranean, offshore wind energy offers a promising solution.

The European Union (EU) green transition has been shaped by various legislations and agreements, such as the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED)⁴, followed by Directive (EU) 2018/2001, which promotes the use of energy from renewable sources, ensuring alignment with recent sustainability goals⁵. Renewable energy is vital for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in line with COP26 and COP27, focusing on advancing the Paris Agreement's goals⁶. The RED and its following updates provide a legal framework to remove barriers to a clean energy transition, encouraging renewable heating, cooling, and transport fuels while promoting investments and lowering renewable energy technology costs⁷. In 2011, the European Commission (EC) introduced the Energy Roadmap 2050 to cut EU greenhouse gas emissions by 80–95% in 2050 compared to 1990⁸. This

was followed by the 2030 Energy and Climate Framework in 2014, which set targets to reduce emissions by at least 40%, increase renewable energy use, and achieve a 27% improvement in energy efficiency by 2030⁹. The European Green Deal, announced in 2019, introduced the EU Adaptation Strategy, replacing the Energy Roadmap 2050. To meet climate goals, a 90% reduction in transport-related greenhouse gas emissions is needed, alongside a targeted increase in inland waterways and short-sea shipping by 25% by 2030 and 50% by 2050¹⁰. However, this will significantly affect marine and coastal environments.

Offshore wind energy, in the form of offshore wind farms, is expected to become a key trend in wind energy production in the Mediterranean. Wind energy remains the EU's second-largest source of power generation capacity, coming close to matching gas installations¹¹. Offshore wind turbines, either seabed-fixed or floating, gain advantages from stronger, more consistent, and more frequent winds than land-based sources turbines¹². As a result, EU legislation has sought to address this emerging sector. In 2020, the EC published a strategy for developing marine renewable energy. In the same year, installed offshore wind capacity in the EU-27 was estimated at 12 GW, and according to forecasts, the EC aims to reach 300 GW of offshore wind capacity in 2050, with an intermediate step of 60 GW in 2030¹³. This epochal shift is anticipated to occur at an unprecedented rate for renewables since, under current policies, the projected installation capacity for 2050 would only be about 90 GW¹⁴. Achieving such targets necessitates the collaboration of all Member States by developing national low-carbon roadmaps. Significant cuts in carbon emissions will also save fossil fuel imports, enhance air quality, and reduce climate change risks as part of this ambitious global action¹⁵.

Growing international interest, reduced costs, and favourable conditions signal a transformative opportunity. Although no operational OWFs exist in the Mediterranean¹⁶, the French Government has taken the lead in the Mediterranean by approving the installation of a pilot floating offshore wind farm, known as “Eoliennes Flottantes du Golfe du Lion” (EFGL)

¹ Plan Bleu, ‘Towards a Sustainable Development of Marine Renewable Energies in the Mediterranean’ (2022) Interreg MED.

² Brundtland, ‘World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future.’ (1987).

³ Angela Delli Paoli and Felice Addeo, ‘Assessing SDGs: A Methodology to Measure Sustainability’ (2019) 6 Athens Journal of Social Sciences 229.

⁴ Directive 2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/77/EC and 2003/30/EC (Text with EEA relevance) 2009.

⁵ Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast) (Text with EEA relevance. [OJ L 328/82].

⁶ Lorenz Moosmann and others, *The COP27 Climate Change Conference. Status of Climate Negotiations and Issues at Stake* (2022).

⁷ Plan Bleu (n 1).

⁸ European Commission, Energy Roadmap 2050 2011 [COM(2011) 885 final].

⁹ Commission, A policy framework for climate and energy from 2020 to 2030 2014 [COM(2014) 15 final].

¹⁰ European Commission, The European Green Deal [COM(2019) 640 final].

¹¹ Maite deCastro and others, ‘An Overview of Offshore Wind Energy Resources in Europe under Present and Future Climate’ (2019) 1436 Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences 70.

¹² Mehmet Bilgili, Abdulkadir Yasar and Erdogan Simsek, ‘Offshore Wind Power Development in Europe and Its Comparison with Onshore Counterpart’ (2011) 15 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 905.

¹³ Plan Bleu (n 1).

¹⁴ An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future 2020 [COM(2020) 741 final].

¹⁵ ‘Floating Offshore Wind Factsheet’ (WindEurope) <<https://windeurope.org/intelligence-platform/product/floating-offshore-wind-factsheet/>> accessed 5 January 2025.

¹⁶ Plan Bleu (n 1).

and two additional pilot projects, while Spain is following suit with the development of the Tramuntana Floating Offshore Wind Farm Project¹⁷. These projects are part of national plans outlined by the European Directive 2014/89/EU¹⁸. The Mediterranean's deep waters and strong winds are well-suited to this innovation, which can access 80% of the world's wind resources in waters deeper than 50 meters¹⁹. The first OWFs were installed in Northern Europe and essentially transposed onshore wind farms to the sea, where the turbines are fixed on masts implanted in the sea bed²⁰. However, the traditional technique has several limitations, notably related to the depth of the implantation zone, which must not exceed 50 metres (m). As a result, they are usually located near the coast, where several environmental risks are identified, such as visual impacts on the landscape and those associated with coastal fishing and commercial shipping²¹.

Given the unique characteristics of the Mediterranean Sea, cost-benefit analyses remain speculative due to the lack of concrete operational examples. Research focuses on OWFs in the North, Baltic, and North Atlantic, which differ from the Mediterranean's diverse shelf morphology and fragile benthic habitats like seagrass meadows and coralligenous reefs²². The limited understanding of OWFs affects the Mediterranean environment, promoting an excessively hopeful perception of OWFs as vital contributors to the green transition while neglecting substantial risks. The long-term impacts of OWFs on marine safety remain insufficiently assessed, with concerns ranging from pollutants released by turbines, buoys, and mooring systems to adverse effects on marine ecosystems and socio-economic conditions. These risks could ultimately undermine the broader objectives of the energy transition. Through a literature review, this essay firstly examines the legislative framework surrounding OWF technology, highlighting its gaps. Analysing the environmental, social, and economic challenges posed by OWFs, it offers a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles to their implementation. The findings stress that inadequate legislation could restrict the benefits of OWFs, leaving social and economic damages unaddressed. The essay illustrates how the energy transition faces significant challenges, revealing that even renewable energy production is not as environmentally benign as often assumed.

EU legislation on sustainable use of marine resources

Since the Rio Conference in 2012, the international community has been actively addressing the sustainable use of marine resources. Building on the foundation of the 1992 Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 14 was adopted in 2015, aiming to "conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development"²³. The Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) was established in 1975 as a multilateral environmental agreement under the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Its primary goal is to protect the marine environment through a coordinated regional approach²⁴. Over time, UNEP/MAP has evolved into a global governance model, which is key in facilitating the negotiation and adoption of the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention) and its associated protocols. With seven protocols under the MAP, the Barcelona Convention is the region's key legally binding multilateral environmental agreement²⁵, which came into force in 2004. Its Contracting Parties (CP) consist of 21 Mediterranean countries and the EU, encompassing the Mediterranean Sea eastward from the Strait of Gibraltar. The Convention allows each party to extend its application to its national territory, ensuring a broad and adaptable scope for regional cooperation.

Cooperation mechanisms, such as those under the Barcelona Convention, aim to coordinate the use of maritime resources, strengthen governance, and foster economic growth while promoting sustainable practices²⁶. These efforts align with broader frameworks of renewable energy policies and marine ecosystem protections. According to Art.4, the CPs agree to take all necessary measures, individually or jointly, to prevent, reduce, and eliminate pollution of the Mediterranean Sea and to protect the marine environment to support sustainable development²⁷. A key component is the Dumping Protocol, entered into force in 1978, and amended in 1995²⁸. Excluding Montenegro, all CPs to the Barcelona Convention are also parties to this protocol, which prohibits dumping activities, incineration at sea, and waste disposal, except for specific materials²⁹. In 2021,

¹⁷ Koldo Diez-Caballero and others, 'Environmental Compatibility of the Parc Tramuntana Offshore Wind Project in Relation to Marine Ecosystems' (2022) 10 *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 898.

¹⁸ Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning 2014.

¹⁹ 'Floating Offshore Wind Factsheet' (n 15).

²⁰ Christophe Le Visage, 'Énergie éolienne en Méditerranée : nouvelle source de conflits ou opportunité de coopération renouvelée ?' (2022) 120 *Confluences Méditerranée* 107.

²¹ Hayley Farr and others, 'Potential Environmental Effects of Deepwater Floating Offshore Wind Energy Facilities' (2021) 207 *Ocean & Coastal Management* 105611.

²² Josep Lloret and others, 'Unravelling the Ecological Impacts of Large-Scale Offshore Wind Farms in the Mediterranean Sea' (2022) 824 *Science of The Total Environment* 153803.

²³ UN General Assembly, 'Resolution Adopted by the General Assembly on 22 December 2015 [on the Report of the Second Committee (A/70/472/Add.9)]70/226. United Nations Conference to Support the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 14: Conserve and Sustainably Use the Oceans.'

²⁴ 'Who We Are | UNEP/MAP' <<https://www.unep.org/uneppmap/who-we-are>> accessed 5 January 2025.

²⁵ 'Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean | EUR-Lex' <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legisum:128084>> accessed 5 January 2025.

²⁶ Plan Bleu (n 1).

²⁷ 'Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean | EUR-Lex' (n 25).

²⁸ UNEP, 'Protocole Relatif à La Prévention et à l'élimination de La Pollution de La Mer Méditerranée Par Les Opérations d'immersion Effectuées Par Les Navires et Aéronefs Ou d'incinération En Mer'.

²⁹ *ibid.*

during the 22nd Meeting of the CPs in Turkey, a decision was made to amend the Annex to the Dumping Protocol. These amendments, binding in the EU under Art. 29 of the Barcelona Convention, revised the criteria for issuing permits for disposal at sea. The updated criteria outline the characteristics and composition of dumped materials and the attributes of dumping sites and deposit methods³⁰. This reflects the CPs' commitment to reducing pollution and ensuring sustainable management of the Mediterranean Sea.

In the Mediterranean, efforts are guided by the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD), adopted during COP19 of the Barcelona Convention in 2016. The MSSD provides a framework to integrate regional, sub-regional, and national policies with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development³¹. This approach aligns with the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) 2016–2025, which states that ecosystem protection is a cornerstone of economic and environmental policy³². It builds on this by targeting the Good Environmental Status (GES) of marine and coastal environments. The MSFD fosters ecosystem-based management, harmonising efforts among 23 coastal and five landlocked EU states and coordinating with non-EU countries to sustainably manage a 5.72 million km² marine area³³. In 2018, the CPs of the Barcelona Convention adopted the Ecosystem Approach (EcAp) and agreed on a roadmap for its implementation in the Mediterranean. The EcAp is a strategy for the integrated management of land, water, and living resources that promotes their conservation and equitable use. As such, it is the guiding principle for policy development and implementation undertaken under the auspices of the Barcelona Convention, such as achieving GES in the Mediterranean marine and coastal environment through informed management decisions based on integrated quantitative assessment and monitoring³⁴. At the Mediterranean level, the EcAp and the MSFD are implemented in synergy and coherence, and they are among the most ambitious international frameworks for marine environmental protection³⁵.

Additional measures include Art.9 of the Integrated Coastal Zone Management Protocol (ICZM) and the Union for the Mediterranean's 2015 Ministerial Declaration, all of which emphasise ecosystem preservation. EU policies, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD), further reinforce these efforts by aiming to achieve good ecological status for water bodies. While its initial goals were delayed due to funding and implementation challenges, the WFD established a governance framework for integrated water management, reducing chemical pollution and linking human activities to their environmental impacts³⁶.

This integrated approach ensures marine ecosystems remain functional and resilient for future generations. After launching the world's first global framework to finance a sustainable Ocean Economy³⁷, the EU introduces its new strategy on Biodiversity for 2030, focusing on “making nature healthy again”³⁸. The strategy boosts the protection of marine ecosystems by expanding the protected areas and stressing the importance of the EcAp for managing human activities at sea. Sustainable innovation presents significant opportunities in green ports, shipping, aquaculture, water management, conservation, recycling, and maritime ecotourism, all key to the region's future. Meanwhile, the Commission emphasised the benefits of sustainable blue economy activities, advocating for an international Blue Economy Sustainability Framework³⁹. However, according to the results of the 2020 report on the first implementation cycles of the MSFD, the EU framework for protecting the marine environment needs to be strengthened⁴⁰. Indeed, GES is achievable only if the pressures on the marine and coastal environment decrease and, therefore, if the uses of the marine and coastal environment that cause these pressures are adjusted. Surprisingly, the notion of GES appears only once in the text of the European Green Deal and only once in the Commission's Communication on the Sustainable Blue Economy⁴¹. This may indicate a persistent lack of integration of marine protection into broader policies or a dominance of economic priorities over marine conservation, even under the guise of climate change adaptation.

³⁰ European Commission, Proposal for a Council Decision on the position to be taken on behalf of the European Union in the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (the 'Barcelona Convention') on the adoption of a Decision to amend the Annex to the Protocol for the Prevention and Elimination of Pollution of the Mediterranean Sea by Dumping from Ships and Aircraft or Incineration at Sea (the 'Dumping Protocol') 2021 [COM(2021) 666 final].

³¹ Raffaele Mancini, 'The Blue Economy in the Mediterranean Region and Opportunities for the Algae Industry' (*IAI Istituto Affari Internazionali*, 12 September 2022) <<https://www.iai.it/en/pubblicazioni/blue-economy-mediterranean-region-and-opportunities-algae-industry>> accessed 5 January 2025.

³² European Commission, Report on the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC) 2020 [COM(2020) 259 final].

³³ *ibid.*

³⁴ SPA/RAC, 'Implementation of the Ecosystem Approach in the Mediterranean' <https://www.rac-spa.org/sites/default/files/ecap/ecap2015_eng.pdf>.

³⁵ Directorate-General for Environment- European Commission, 'Marine Environment' (2 December 2024) <https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/marine-environment_en> accessed 5 January 2025.

³⁶ Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy 2000.

³⁷ 'Pioneering Global Framework for Sustainable Ocean Finance Launched at Our Ocean Global Summit' (*European Investment Bank*) <<https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2018-273-pioneering-global-framework-for-sustainable-ocean-finance-launched-at-our-ocean-global-summit>> accessed 8 January 2025.

³⁸ Bassetti, 'Nature-Based Solutions - Foresight' <<https://www.climatefore-sight.eu/seeds/nature-based-solutions/>> accessed 5 January 2025.

³⁹ European Commission: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, *Sustainability Criteria for the Blue Economy: Main Report* (Publications Office of the European Union 2021).

⁴⁰ An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future (n 14).

⁴¹ European Commission, A new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future 2021 [COM(2021) 240 final].

To address this, the EU approved a taxonomy defining criteria for economic activities contributing to climate adaptation and prioritising adaptation solutions⁴². Furthermore, aware of the scale and diversity of its natural heritage, the EU has been very attentive to preserving its ecosystems and has created an extensive body of legislation to protect and enhance Mediterranean biodiversity. The Nature Directives were made to ensure a healthy natural world in the EU through a legal framework for protecting species and natural habitats. These directives establish the Natura 2000, a network of nature protection areas comprising Special Areas of Conservation and Special Protection Areas designated under the Habitats Directive⁴³ and the Birds Directive⁴⁴. Natura 2000 ensures the conservation of rare, threatened, or endemic species, including all wild bird species in the EU, through protection, management, and monitoring measures. It covers 18% of the EU's land area and 6% of its sea area and is currently predominantly active on land⁴⁵. Still, significant gaps are present concerning the marine environment, and only 50% of all Natura sites have management plans with conservation objectives and measures. In 2014, the European Commission conducted a comprehensive evaluation of the Nature Directives, known as the "Fitness Check," to assess their effectiveness⁴⁶. The evaluation confirmed that the directives are fit for purpose and capable of improving species and habitat conditions; however, their success depends on practical implementation.

EU legislation on OWFs

When discussing wind energy, a key distinction is between energy generated by onshore and offshore wind farms. OWFs consist of multiple wind turbines that convert the wind's kinetic energy into electricity⁴⁷. In the Mediterranean, OWFs are vital to the Blue Economy, a sector generating significant regional income. The Blue Economy encompasses traditional maritime activities such as fishing, aquaculture, coastal tourism and emerging sectors such as renewable energy and marine biotechnologies⁴⁸. The Sustainable Blue Economy focuses on clean technologies, renewable energy, and circular material flows to secure long-term social and economic stability

within planetary boundaries⁴⁹. It seeks to balance the optimal use of maritime natural capital with human and social capital, advancing sustainable development, social equity, and reduced ecological risks. The EU's taxonomy for climate change mitigation, outlined in Regulation (EU) 2020/852 and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088, provides a framework for determining whether economic activities and investments qualify as environmentally sustainable, including provisions for the marine environment⁵⁰. The regulation focuses on transitioning to renewable energy, reducing fossil fuel reliance, and promoting carbon-neutral energy sources. It allows activities with no viable low-carbon alternatives as long as they limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. Such activities must comply with strict GHG emissions standards and support the development of low-carbon alternatives.

Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2139 establishes the general framework for determining whether an economic activity and its investments qualify as environmentally sustainable and includes several chapters related to the marine environment⁵¹. It ensures the conservation of rare, threatened, and endemic species, including all wild bird species in the EU, through measures for their protection, management, and monitoring. It also highlights the restoration of wetlands and the development of renewable energy sources such as wind, ocean, hydropower, geothermal energy, and cogeneration technologies. Furthermore, it states that offshore wind projects must not hinder achieving GES as defined by the MSFD, requiring measures to prevent or mitigate impacts on biodiversity and seabed integrity, supported by an environmental impact assessment and necessary mitigation and compensation measures. However, the references to the proper use of offshore wind turbines contained in the Regulation are insufficient to address their wide-ranging environmental impacts, including harm to marine ecosystems and pollutant emissions during their creation and dismantling. Furthermore, their buoys or mooring systems could contain one or more environmentally hazardous substances.

Natura 2000 sites and the Special Protection Areas for birds, considered the wealthiest areas in terms of biodiversity, must be avoided and preserved from the implantation of OWFs, notably because if their integrity were affected, their legal status would be at risk. These areas, rich in flora and fauna of

⁴² 'EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities - European Commission' <https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en> accessed 8 January 2025.

⁴³ Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora [OJ L206].

⁴⁴ Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds (Codified version) - EU monitor [OJ L 207].

⁴⁵ European Commission A policy framework for climate and energy in the period from 2020 to 2030 (n 9).

⁴⁶ *ibid*.

⁴⁷ Ministère Aménagement du Territoire Transition Écologique, 'Éolien Terrestre' (2017) <<https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/eolien-terrestre#scroll-nav%20%201>> accessed 20 April 2022.

⁴⁸ European Commission A new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future (n 41).

⁴⁹ WWF, 'Principles for a Sustainable Blue Economy' (2015) <https://wwfint.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/15_1471_blue_economy_6_pages_final.pdf>.

⁵⁰ 'Regulation - 2020/852 - EN - Taxonomy Regulation - EUR-Lex' <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj/eng>> accessed 6 January 2025.

⁵¹ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2139 of 4 June 2021 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing the technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation or climate change adaptation and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives (Text with EEA relevance) [OJ L442/1].

immense heritage value, are subject to a strict obligation to ensure their protection, with the risk of condemnation by the member states involved in case of failure⁵². The Habitats Directive does not prohibit wind farms in Natura 2000 sites but requires case-by-case analysis for their siting. An assessment must demonstrate that the project will not have significant adverse impacts on the site, particularly on habitats, including direct loss, degradation, fragmentation, species disturbance, or other indirect effects on environmental quality⁵³. The study must consider the extent and magnitude of the impacts and assess different active projects in the area. Indeed, if well combined with other economic activities, such as those linked to other renewable energy sources, the negative impacts of offshore wind energy installations could be reduced. At the same time, biodiversity in these zones may even increase. However, there is no legal basis at the national or EU level to prevent such an occurrence.

The EC guidance document on wind energy developments and Natura 2000 sites was designed to align with new EU policies and legislation on renewable energy and offshore wind technology⁵⁴. It clarifies the application of the Natura Directives, updates the 2011 guidance on wind farms in Natura 2000 sites, and highlights the need for further guidance, knowledge, and best practices to reconcile the objectives of different policies, underscoring the importance of further exploration in this area. However, although official documents, EC communications are non-legally binding⁵⁵. Thus, the guidance document is not legally enforceable; its primary aim is to inform about particular elements of relevant EU legislation, especially regarding the effects of wind energy on biodiversity and effective practices to mitigate these effects⁵⁶. Its non-binding nature risks limiting credibility and enforcement. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a case-by-case analysis before building these constructions. This highlights gaps in EU legislation, where progress in one area may hinder others.

Environmental challenges

As the offshore wind industry grows, its impacts on marine ecosystems remain insufficiently explored. The estimated 25-to-30-year lifecycle of an OWF encompasses multiple stages, including raw material extraction, component manufacturing,

installation, maintenance, and decommissioning⁵⁷. OWFs reduce emissions but can harm aquatic ecosystems, with biodiversity protection often overlooked in offshore energy areas. Floating technology holds significant potential as it overcomes the limitations of traditional wind farms by harnessing stronger, more consistent winds⁵⁸. Floating wind turbines, typically with horizontal axes and two or three blades, are anchored to the seabed by cables and towed into position. These turbines can have capacities of 15 MW or more, with blade lengths exceeding 100 m, and are installed in clusters connected by seabed cables⁵⁹. They can operate in any water depth, allowing them to be placed across the continental shelf, far from shore, avoiding visual and logistical issues linked to coastal fishing and shipping. The environmental impact of electricity generation from a floating wind power plant is not significantly different from that of conventional offshore wind power plants, provided that it operates with a higher capacity factor⁶⁰. However, floating technology introduces additional risks, including those from suction anchors, subsea cables, and ballast water in internal tanks⁶¹. It may have a larger environmental footprint due to potential repairs onshore⁶². Underwater cables could limit accessible fishing zones⁶³, and debates persist over the potential loss of biodiversity in benthic and pelagic habitats, which house diverse marine life, from molluscs and sponges to fish and birds⁶⁴. To mitigate these impacts, policymakers must apply the Precautionary Principle⁶⁵, as outlined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and reflected in the MSFD and the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD), which promotes sustainable maritime growth⁶⁶.

Impact assessments should address all OWF development stages. Key concerns include visual and acoustic stress, habitat loss, pollution, water turbidity, bird collisions, electric fields, artificial reefs, and maintenance effects⁶⁷. Additionally, marine

⁵⁷ Anna Garcia-Teruel and others, 'Life Cycle Assessment of Floating Offshore Wind Farms: An Evaluation of Operation and Maintenance' (2022) 307 *Applied Energy* 118067.

⁵⁸ Plan Bleu (n 1).

⁵⁹ Le Visage (n 20).

⁶⁰ Jan Weinzettel and others, 'Life Cycle Assessment of a Floating Offshore Wind Turbine' (2009) 34 *Renewable Energy* 742.

⁶¹ Garcia-Teruel and others (n 57).

⁶² Barbara Mendecka and Lidia Lombardi, 'Life Cycle Environmental Impacts of Wind Energy Technologies: A Review of Simplified Models and Harmonization of the Results' (2019) 111 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 462.

⁶³ Le Visage (n 20).

⁶⁴ 'Environmental Factor Guideline - Benthic Communities and Habitats | EPA Western Australia' <<https://www.epa.wa.gov.au/policies-guidance/environmental-factor-guideline-benthic-communities-and-habitats>> accessed 6 January 2025.

⁶⁵ EUR-Lex, 'Precautionary Principle' <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legissum:precautionary_principle> accessed 9 January 2025.

⁶⁶ Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning (n 18).

⁶⁷ Maria Defingou and others, *PHAROS4MPAS - Safeguarding Marine Protected Areas in the Growing Mediterranean Blue Economy. Capitalization Report for the Offshore Wind Energy Sector.* (2019).

⁵² F Gouty, 'Éolien en mer: le rapport complexe entre énergies renouvelables, biodiversité et sites protégés' (*Actu-Environnement*, 25 August 2021) <<https://www.actu-environnement.com/ae/news/eolien-mer-offshore-rapport-energies-renouvelables-biodiversite-sites-natura-2000-38068.php4>> accessed 5 January 2025.

⁵³ S Fabrégat, 'Éolien : planifier pour réduire, voire inverser, les impacts sur la biodiversité' (*Actu-Environnement*, 20 January 2021) <<https://www.actu-environnement.com/ae/news/eoliennes-biodiversite-planification-impacts-renouvelables-36907.php4>> accessed 10 January 2025.

⁵⁴ Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), *Guidance Document on Wind Energy Developments and EU Nature Legislation* (Publications Office of the European Union 2020) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/095188>> accessed 5 January 2025.

⁵⁵ EUR-Lex, 'Atypical Acts' <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legissum:114535>> accessed 6 January 2025.

⁵⁶ Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission) (n 50).

traffic and OWF maintenance threaten marine fauna like mammals and sea turtles, with the northern Mediterranean and the Strait of Gibraltar being key hotspots for ship strikes⁶⁸. Marine fauna, particularly mammals, rely on sound for essential survival activities such as communication, prey identification, and orientation. Human-made noise from shipping, construction, and military operations disrupts vital functions. It harms animal welfare, with pile driving for offshore wind farms being a significant source of undersea noise pollution⁶⁹, causing physical stress and injuries and alter marine population dynamics. Macroscopic pollution from household and industrial waste and chemical pollution from toxic substances like oil spills and underwater corrosion harm aquatic life. During OWF construction and operation, waste discharge also poses risks, including entanglement⁷⁰. Toxic metals from sacrificial anodes that protect submerged structures can dissolve into the environment, forming toxic bonds with other elements⁷¹. Risks include accidents at turbine sites caused by storms, fires, or ship collisions, which could cause oil or chemical spills. Wind turbine accidents are thus a significant concern⁷².

Electromagnetic fields generated by underwater power cables transmitting electricity from OWFs to the coast have serious impacts on marine ecosystems⁷³. The primary concern is the effect on animals that use the Earth's geomagnetic field for orientation and rely on electroreception to hunt, with potential disruptions to these critical functions⁷⁴. Furthermore, energy transmission through cables generates heat, raising their temperature to 70°C and warming the surrounding environment⁷⁵. When cables are laid above the seabed, convection transfers heat to the surrounding seawater, impacting the seabed ecosystem depending on the cable type and proximity. Additionally, artificial lights used during construction, operation, maintenance, or at night for obstruction warnings can pose a threat, especially to nocturnal migratory birds and sea turtles. These species may become disoriented and attracted to the turbines, leading to potential collisions between seabirds or migratory birds and wind turbines, especially when birds pass through areas swept

by rotors⁷⁶. Actual fatalities are hard to track, so researchers focus on collision and avoidance rates to estimate the risk. Sensitivity maps can help identify areas with high collision potential, aiding strategic planning, while temporary turbine shutdowns during mass migration events have effectively reduced risks⁷⁷. Identifying at-risk species requires considerable resources, with new systems using radar and cameras for real-time bird detection. Other strategies include altering blade patterns, using ultraviolet-reflecting paints, and deploying bird deterrents⁷⁸.

Offshore wind turbines, typically installed at depths of up to 50 meters, are often placed in coastal areas rich in marine biodiversity, leading to significant environmental impacts. Birds are attracted to the bases of turbines, increasing the risk of collision with rotating blades, which can disrupt migration routes⁷⁹. Many seabirds in the Mediterranean, some endangered or threatened⁸⁰, breed in the region before migrating to the Atlantic. Additionally, wind farms pose collision risks to migratory and local bats. Turtles and other mammals are also at risk from construction and turbine operations, such as collisions or entanglement with submarine cables. Furthermore, new artificial substrates can introduce non-native species, disrupting local biodiversity⁸¹. OWF anchors and cables can disturb Maerl and seagrass habitats, leading to habitat loss and displacement of species. Geotechnical construction methods can also remobilise nutrients and contaminants, further impacting species' survival and Maerl, which provide shelter for marine organisms and act as carbon reservoirs⁸². Seagrass meadows, especially those formed by the endangered *Posidonia oceanica*⁸³, are crucial ecosystems that support fish, molluscs, and other species⁸⁴.

Secondary impacts of OWFs are those not directly caused by the turbines but resulting from their presence. The "reef effect" is generated when the construction of OWFs creates new artificial substrates, particularly turbine foundations, which become artificial reefs⁸⁵. These reefs attract new marine life, especially in sandy habitats, boosting local biodiversity. While native species colonise these reefs, some species may be absent,

⁶⁸ Manuel Carrillo, 'Increasing Numbers of Ship Strikes in the Canary Islands: Proposals for Immediate Action to Reduce Risk of Vessel-Whale Collisions' (2010) J. CETACEAN RES. MANAGE. Journal of Cetacean Research and Management 131.

⁶⁹ Habib-ur-Rehman Solangi, 'Undersea Noise Pollution and Harm: Source, Impacts and International Legal Control' <https://brill.com/view/journals/cjel/3/2/article-p203_4.xml> accessed 9 January 2025.

⁷⁰ Lloret and others (n 22).

⁷¹ T Kirchgeorg and others, 'Emissions from Corrosion Protection Systems of Offshore Wind Farms: Evaluation of the Potential Impact on the Marine Environment' (2018) 136 Marine Pollution Bulletin 257.

⁷² Sobhan Arisian and others, 'Wind Turbine Accidents: A Data Mining Study' (2017) 11 IEEE Systems Journal 1567.

⁷³ I Donázar-Aramendía and others, 'Assessing the Effects of Electromagnetic Fields Generated by Submarine Power Cables on the Soft-Bottom Community: An Ecological in-situ Study' (2025) 266 Environmental Research 120573.

⁷⁴ Defingou and others (n 67).

⁷⁵ CJ Emeana and others, 'The Thermal Regime around Buried Submarine High-Voltage Cables' (2016) 206 Geophysical Journal International 1051.

⁷⁶ Defingou and others (n 67).

⁷⁷ Plan Bleu (n 1).

⁷⁸ Defingou and others (n 67).

⁷⁹ CNPN, Autosaisine du CNPN sur le développement de l'énergie offshore en France et ses impacts sur la biodiversité, le patrimoine naturel et les paysages 2021.

⁸⁰ 'Ten Seabirds Added to the Mediterranean List of Endangered or Threatened Species | UNEP MAP' <<https://www.unep.org/uneppmap/news/news/ten-seabirds-added-mediterranean-list-endangered-or-threatened-species>> accessed 6 January 2025.

⁸¹ Lloret and others (n 22).

⁸² Carmen Barberá and others, 'Conservation and Management of NE Atlantic and Mediterranean Maerl Beds' (2003) 13 Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems S65.

⁸³ Luca Telesca and others, 'Seagrass Meadows (*Posidonia Oceanica*) Distribution and Trajectories of Change' (2015) 5 Scientific Reports 12505.

⁸⁴ Defingou and others (n 67).

⁸⁵ Plan Bleu (n 1).

and mobile species, like fish and crabs, may need to relocate due to lost habitat⁸⁶. This effect can benefit fish and crustaceans, though outcomes depend on the type of reef and native species characteristics, as invasive species may spread through these artificial reefs. The EC guidelines stress that impacts in protected areas must not harm habitats' or species' integrity or conservation status⁸⁷. The "reserve effect" increases fish survival rates due to restricted fishing near OWFs, though higher fishing pressure may negate the "spillover effect" of no-fishing zones⁸⁸. Moreover, offshore wind turbines can reduce wind speed downstream, increasing turbulence and altering ocean dynamics. They may also cause upwelling and downwelling around the wind farm. Anchoring systems can stir up suspended sediments, leading to persistent water turbidity and bathymetry changes. Pollution from turbines or the dissolution of sacrificial anodes can further degrade water quality. However, long-term effects remain insufficiently studied, and a comprehensive and reliable assessment of these cumulative impacts is needed⁸⁹.

Socio-economic challenges

Little research and monitoring exists on the socio-economic impacts of OWFs in the Mediterranean, which are often overshadowed by environmental and economic concerns. Cumulative impacts include effects on employment, economic growth, housing, local services, community welfare, and conflicts with sectors like tourism and fisheries. From an economic perspective, OWFs affect employment, Gross Value Added (GVA), and coastal industries such as fishing, shipping, and recreation. OWF construction and maintenance phases generate jobs, focusing on training programs and local supply chain opportunities⁹⁰. They improve infrastructure, especially ports, and generate socio-economic benefits during construction. However, social impacts include housing pressures and quality of life, with developers potentially offering housing support. Tourism is a fundamental economic driver in the Mediterranean regions, especially in coastal recreational activities such as sailing, scuba diving, swimming, and bird and whale watching. The creation of OWFs can limit these activities, and the economic revenue losses could be significant⁹¹. Many Mediterranean coastal states have narrow continental shelves, and OWFs are planned relatively close to the coast, which can impact the visual image of the seascape to lead tourists

to move away from beaches to more natural seascapes, raising concerns for local communities affected by the loss of economic income⁹². Thus, Community Benefit Agreements recognise local involvement, provided to the community as a gesture of appreciation for their participation in projects deemed to be in the national interest, rather than as direct compensation for local impacts⁹³. Community acceptance of offshore projects is crucial, as residents may perceive these farms as part of industrialising the sea, reinforcing multiple economic worries.

Banning fishing in areas where OWFs are installed could seriously affect this industry, especially the small-scale fisheries in the area, which are widely present in the Mediterranean coastal states⁹⁴. In addition, fishing is restricted during the farms' construction phases, and the construction settlements could affect fishery resources⁹⁵. The ban on fishing could also jeopardise the scientific surveys of fishery resources that have been fundamental in evaluating developments in the areas throughout the years, as the farms could increase local underwater biodiversity by excluding these areas from fishing. Sensitive buffer zones between OWFs and MPAs could partially protect sensitive species, although further studies are needed. However, the most efficient turbine installation areas often overlap with multiple MPAs, offering ideal wind and bathymetric conditions. Focusing solely on technical criteria, energy companies may select these sites for OWFs without fully considering potential ecological impacts. Given the high traffic in Mediterranean waters, OWFs pose a risk of collision between commercial and passenger vessels, further reducing navigable space in one of the world's most crowded seas⁹⁶. Moreover, it augments traffic density on other available routes, increasing the risk of collision.

Wind energy production depends on materials with a high supply risk. The new wind turbines, where a generator converts mechanical energy into electrical energy, are programmed to achieve maximum efficiency and the lowest possible energy costs. Fluctuating wind energy makes variable-speed generators, like permanent magnet (PM) generators, and blades with high strength-to-weight ratios and fatigue resistance the most suitable options. Materials must be resistant to corrosion, wind, and extreme weather conditions. Usually, the main components of the turbines are made of steel and manufactured from a mixture of iron ore, carbon and other elements, including nickel, molybdenum, titanium, manganese, vanadium or cobalt, and the blades are made of fibreglass and resin. However, the production of these components relies

⁸⁶ Danish Energy Agency, 'Offshore Wind Farms and the Environment: Danish Experiences from Horns Rev and Nysted' (Danish Energy Agency 2006) <<https://tethys.pnnl.gov/publications/offshore-wind-farms-environment-danish-experiences-horns-rev-nysted>> accessed 10 January 2025.

⁸⁷ Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission) (n 50).

⁸⁸ Denis Lacroix and Sylvain Pioch, 'The Multi-Use in Wind Farm Projects: More Conflicts or a Win-Win Opportunity?' (2011) 24 *Aquatic Living Resources*.

⁸⁹ Han Lindeboom and others, 'Offshore Wind Park Monitoring Programmes, Lessons Learned and Recommendations for the Future' (2015) 756 *Hydrobiologia*.

⁹⁰ Bridget Durning and others, *Guidance on Assessing the Socio-Economic Impacts of Offshore Wind Farms (OWFs)*. Full Text Available from the Oxford Brookes University Repository via This DOI Link: [10.24384/Ax1s-Jr48](https://doi.org/10.24384/Ax1s-Jr48) (2020).

⁹¹ Lloret and others (n 22).

⁹² Vanja Westerberg, Jette Bredahl Jacobsen and Robert Lifran, 'Offshore Wind Farms in the Mediterranean Seascape: A Tourist Appeal or a Tourist Repellent', 18. *Annual Conference EAERE* (European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE) INT 2011) <<https://hal.science/hal-01594425>> accessed 6 January 2025.

⁹³ Durning and others (n 90).

⁹⁴ Plan Bleu (n 1).

⁹⁵ Le Visage (n 20).

⁹⁶ *ibid.*

heavily on several Rare Earth Elements (REEs), including neodymium-iron-boron and dysprosium, which are primarily sourced outside the EU⁹⁷, mainly from China (54%) and Latin America (29%)⁹⁸. Demand for these materials is expected to rise significantly by 2050 compared to current levels⁹⁹.

Raw materials sourced outside the EU create economic dependence on non-EU countries. This reliance raises concerns about the feasibility and long-term effects of the green transition. While renewable energy costs are decreasing and expected to play a significant role in decarbonisation, the growing demand for minerals will lead to increased extraction, with potential environmental impacts if not managed responsibly, as the mining sector accounts for 2–11% of global energy consumption¹⁰⁰. Climate-smart mining practices are necessary to prevent shifting emissions from power generation to mining. Moreover, metal prices, particularly for generators containing REEs, heavily influence wind turbine costs. High international demand and limited availability of raw materials pose risks to the global transition to sustainable energy. The bottleneck goes from a high risk for raw materials to a medium risk for the supply of processed components and is almost undetectable for assemblies. Concerns stem from China's near-monopoly on REEs and PM manufacturing, with potential price fluctuations due to trade disputes, as seen during the 2011 crisis when China imposed strict market restrictions¹⁰¹.

Many European countries have started intense campaigns of seabed exploration to detect the presence of REEs and proceed with their extraction. Polymetallic nodules proliferate in these environments and appear to be the new paradise for REEs¹⁰². Extractive activities are costly in terms of machinery used for extraction, mainly because of their impact on marine ecosystems. Under UNESCO's objective of chart graphing 80% of seabeds by the end of the decade, many exploratory activities have already been performed, which open the way for future extractive activity in the concerned seas¹⁰³. The UNEP Global Environmental Alert Service reports that massive seabed sulphide deposits containing copper, lead, zinc, silver, and other metals are primarily found under national jurisdiction, with polymetallic nodules in the equatorial Pacific and cobalt-rich

crusts in the western Pacific¹⁰⁴. Exploring deep seabeds is often followed by exploiting these areas, which are still mysterious and widely unknown. However, deep-sea mining presents environmental threats. Extraction involves pulverising mineral crusts pumped to vessels, releasing pollutants, noise, light, and invasive species. The light affects deep-water species, while the altered water composition reduces oxygen and clouds the environment¹⁰⁵. Mining can also destroy vent communities¹⁰⁶ which take years to recover¹⁰⁷, and suspend sediments, damaging bottom-dwelling species.

To capitalise on valuable discoveries, the rush for control in the Mediterranean has intensified as coastal states establish Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) to manage marine resources and protection, whose legal basis is established in The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)¹⁰⁸. Indeed, unlike the exploitation of hydrocarbons, the appropriation of wind resources requires states to create EEZs for wind energy¹⁰⁹, but the area's geography and the territories' proximity along the coasts result in overlapping claims over EEZs, leading to further state disputes. The seabed has increasingly become a contested space, with the risk of militarisation becoming the norm as well as growing threats to underwater infrastructure, as exemplified by the deployment of deep-operating drones by the French Navy¹¹⁰. Ideally, joint management would benefit the international community. However, current legislation on the high seas is weak and non-binding, and each state has sovereign rights and environmental protection obligations within its EEZ. The Mediterranean Sea was historically excluded from maritime territorialisation, with coastal states limiting their claims to territorial seas and establishing fisheries and ecological protection zones until the 1990s¹¹¹. The discovery of offshore fossil energy deposits in the Mediterranean has highlighted the need for new boundaries, leading to efforts to establish EEZs¹¹².

⁹⁷ 'Extraction En Eaux Troubles | Cairn.Info' (2022) <<https://shs-cairn.info.acces.bibl.ulaval.ca/magazine-socialter-2022-3-page-56?lang=fr&tab=auteurs>> accessed 5 January 2025.

⁹⁸ European Commission, Joint Research Centre, 'Critical Raw Materials for Strategic Technologies and Sectors in the EU A Foresight Study' (Publications Office of the European Union, 2020).

⁹⁹ Kirsten Lori Hund and others, 'Minerals for Climate Action : The Mineral Intensity of the Clean Energy Transition' Text/HTML.

¹⁰⁰ Joel Guilbaud, 'Hybrid Renewable Power Systems for the Mining Industry: System Costs, Reliability Costs, and Portfolio Cost Risks' (2016).

¹⁰¹ European Commission, Joint Research Centre (n 98).

¹⁰² 'Extraction En Eaux Troubles | Cairn.Info' (n 97).

¹⁰³ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁴ United Nations Environment Programme, 'Wealth in the Oceans: Deep Sea Mining on the Horizon?: UNEP Global Environmental Alert Service (GEAS) - May 2014' <<https://wedocs.unep.org/xmlui/handle/20.500.11822/8903>> accessed 6 January 2025.

¹⁰⁵ UNEP (n 28).

¹⁰⁶ Antony Joseph, 'Chapter 6 - Seafloor Hot Chimneys and Cold Seeps: Mysterious Life Around Them' in Antony Joseph (ed), *Investigating Seafloors and Oceans* (Elsevier 2017) <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128093573000060>> accessed 6 January 2025.

¹⁰⁷ Cindy Lee Van Dover, 'Mining Seafloor Massive Sulphides and Biodiversity: What Is at Risk?' (2011) 68 ICES Journal of Marine Science 341.

¹⁰⁸ UN, Multilateral United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (with annexes, final act and procès-verbaux of rectification of the final act dated 3 March 1986 and 26 July 1993). 1982.

¹⁰⁹ Le Visage (n 20).

¹¹⁰ 'Extraction En Eaux Troubles | Cairn.Info' (n 97).

¹¹¹ Martine Pellen-Blin, Philippe Dézéraud and Gérard Valin, 'La territorialisation de la Méditerranée à l'origine de nouveaux équilibres stratégiques' (2019) 822 Revue Défense Nationale 17.

¹¹² Le Visage (n 20).

Finally, raw material processing has a high environmental impact. New EU technologies could improve sector competitiveness and secure a sustainable supply of primary and secondary raw materials. Technological developments, such as iron nitride-based PM technology, which is cheaper and more abundant, are expected to be commercialised in the coming years, as well as the implementation of recycling techniques for materials already present. Adequate legislation and practices for these materials' collection and recycling capacity should be rapidly implemented in the EU. Labelling systems indicating the type of PM can help to improve the recycling process and achieve more efficient results. This would secure the magnet industries in the short term¹¹³. However, heavy metal recycling technologies are still in their early stages of development and face many difficulties, such as the problematic separation of components, which makes the whole recycling process very costly, and the lack of information on the REEs content of different products. Technological advancements and improved recycling practices can reduce environmental impacts and enhance sustainability. However, efficient heavy metal recycling technologies and robust legislation are essential for long-term competitiveness and sustainability.

Discussion and conclusion

Climate change is a major driver of biodiversity loss in the Mediterranean, affecting terrestrial and marine ecosystems. While substantial legislation exists to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and pollution on land and enhance environmental protection, the frameworks for safeguarding marine resources need to be updated to include recent technological developments in marine energy. This gap presents a significant challenge, as it risks prioritising climate change mitigation goals at the expense of marine ecosystems conservation. Consequently, achieving a Blue Economy that aligns with the GES may be challenging. OWFs are often championed for their role in decarbonisation, but their potential negative impacts on marine environments remain insufficiently assessed. Legislative inconsistencies further complicate this issue. As a result, the green transition carries significant costs, creating additional challenges in balancing environmental protection with renewable energy development.

In the Mediterranean, wind power is widely regarded as a sustainable solution to climate change. While wind energy is pollution-free and offers a long-term sustainable energy source,

its uses may also cause irreversible damage to vulnerable marine ecosystems. The lack of sufficient research into the long-term effects of OWFs, coupled with gaps in existing legislation, impedes progress in reducing carbon footprints while safeguarding its unique marine environments. The region's distinctive characteristics, including its depth and environmental sensitivity, necessitate floating wind technology, a solution still in its early stages and not yet deployed at scale. The environmental impacts, feasibility, and long-term sustainability of floating wind farms remain poorly explored, underscoring the urgent need for comprehensive research and stronger regulatory frameworks before large-scale installations are implemented. Additional environmental concerns include the potential impact of seabed exploration and deep-sea mining, which could further threaten marine biodiversity. Addressing these issues requires a balanced approach, integrating renewable energy development with robust environmental protection measures to preserve the Mediterranean's unique ecosystems for future generations.

The essay highlights the urgent need for legislative reform to address immediate challenges and develop a sustainable wind energy strategy in the Mediterranean. While offshore wind energy can reduce fossil fuel reliance, vague legislation coupled with limited research on socioeconomic and environmental impacts hinders progress. Despite efforts to protect maritime heritage, EU measures remain inadequate, requiring expanded protected areas and collaborative regional management. Moreover, diversifying the REE supply chain is critical to reducing EU dependence on China, achievable through partnerships and exploratory projects in northern EU countries like Sweden, Finland, Germany, and Norway¹¹⁴. New studies on the manufacturing, operation, disposal, and recycling of wind turbines are needed, alongside international guidelines and pilot projects, to ensure sustainability and long-term viability. While offshore wind can contribute to sustainable development goals, its risks must be addressed through innovation, research, and a holistic regional approach. Otherwise, it may ultimately fall short of expectations as the "New Eldorado."

Ethical approval and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

¹¹³Hund and others (n 99).

¹¹⁴European Commission, Joint Research Centre (n 98).

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Laura Castro-Santos

Universidade da Coruna, A Coruña, Galicia, Spain

The aim of the paper is to analyze the need of legislation in order to address environmental, social and economic aspects of offshore wind energy in the Mediterranean Sea.

I have some comments:

1. Page 6. "*When discussing wind energy, a key distinction is between energy generated by onshore and offshore wind farms. OWFs consist of multiple wind turbines that convert the wind's kinetic energy into electricity*". The definition of OWF could be the same as Onshore wind farms. You need to explain that in offshore the energy is generated offshore.

2. Page 7. "*Floating wind turbines, typically with horizontal axes and two or three blades, are anchored to the seabed by cables and towed into position.*" They are anchored to the seabed using mooring (chain or fiber).

3. "*Offshore wind turbines, typically installed at depths of up to 50 meters,...*" Before you talked about floating offshore and now you are talking about offshore wind in general (up to 60 meters only fixed systems can be installed). You need to separate the analysis of fixed offshore wind and floating offshore wind, because floating has less impact on environment.

4. In section "Environmental challenges" I think that you need to enumerate (with numbers) each of them, because you repeat a lot of issues during this section (such as the sacrificial anodes, etc.). I think that you need to separate between fixed and floating offshore wind.

5. The title "Cost-beneficiaries analysis" is not clear, because you do not calculate it with equations. Therefore, the title should be changed.

6. I think that the "Mediterranean" in the title is not clear because the text is very generic and it is not applied directly to Mediterranean Sea. Firstly, it is important to know the areas of the Mediterranean Sea where fixed and floating offshore wind can be developed and secondly, you need to explain the differences between this two types of offshore wind in order to introduce the environmental and social issues.

Please, ensure that the text is reviewed considering all these comments.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Partly

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Partly

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Partly

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.**Reviewer Expertise:** Offshore wind**I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.**

Author Response 28 Jun 2025

Marta Avesani

I thank the reviewer for the constructive feedback. In response to the reviewer's input regarding the definition of offshore wind farms (OWFs), the text has been revised to clarify that OWFs are located at sea and utilise marine wind resources to generate electricity. This clarification distinctly differentiates OWFs from onshore wind farms, which are situated on land.

The description of floating wind turbines has been updated to accurately state that they are anchored to the seabed using mooring systems, which typically consist of chains or synthetic fibers, rather than cables.

This revision ensures technical accuracy in describing the anchoring methods used for floating offshore wind technology.

The text has been revised to clearly differentiate between fixed-bottom and floating offshore wind technologies, specifying their respective depth ranges and associated environmental impacts. This distinction provides a clearer and more accurate analysis by addressing the unique characteristics and effects of each technology type.

The "Environmental challenges" section has been revised to clearly enumerate each challenge, improving the overall structure and reducing repetition. Additionally, the discussion has been separated to address the environmental impacts of fixed-bottom and floating offshore wind systems individually, ensuring a more precise and organized analysis. The title has been revised to reflect the qualitative nature of the analysis better, has been clarified to more accurately reflect the focus on the Mediterranean Sea, replacing the previous "Cost-beneficiaries analysis" with

“The Mediterranean Offshore Wind Turn: Lessons, Risks, and Regional Reflections.”

The text has been revised to include a detailed description of specific areas within the Mediterranean that are suitable for both fixed and floating offshore wind development. Additionally, the technical differences between these two types of offshore wind technologies are explained to establish a clear foundation for the subsequent discussion of their environmental and social impacts. This revision ensures the analysis is both regionally relevant and technically grounded.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 10 April 2025

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Barry Johnston

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The title of the manuscript is ‘*Cost-benefit analysis of the offshore wind power transition in the Mediterranean: Towards a “New Eldorado”?*’, however the manuscript does not provide a quantitative study on this topic, instead is a collection of qualitative data and observations on primarily how offshore wind energy may impact, biodiversity, supply chains and economic development. The manuscript has a substantial volume of relevant information, most of which is well structured. Where appropriate, the manuscript uses examples from existing offshore wind locations. It draws comparisons, considering that the EU member states are considering offshore wind deployment in the Mediterranean, which is a valuable exercise.

Several issues should be addressed before the manuscript is suitable for acceptance.

- Firstly, a general observation is that several statements may be correct but are not supported by references in the text.

For example, ‘OWFs reduce emissions but can harm aquatic ecosystems, with biodiversity protection often overlooked in offshore energy areas.’ This is a significant statement without any reference or supporting evidence.

There are multiple other examples of this. Please review the manuscript thoroughly and ensure that data or a source supports any statement.

- The manuscript's structure does not always seem coherent. It would benefit from illustrations or flowcharts depicting how the author sees some of the interactions.

For example, the paper's structure leaves some duplication, where references to turbine technology appear in multiple sections. It may be worthwhile to reconsider the headings and structure of the manuscript so that sections fit together, and the manuscript flows better.

- Some of the references are not the most current.

For example, ‘2030 Energy and Climate Framework in 2014, which set targets to reduce emissions

by at least 40%, increase renewable energy use, and achieve a 27% improvement in energy efficiency by 2030'. I don't think this is current, and these targets have been revised.

There are other examples of dated references. Please check the sources and ensure that the data presented is current.

- Some technical details about offshore wind as a technology need to be improved; some statements are open to misinterpretation.

For example, some text refers to technologies still in prototype stages and may not reach commercial development. Still, the manuscript reads as if these technologies are at commercially readily available.

For example, page 7 reads 'These turbines can have capacities of 15 MW or more, with blade lengths exceeding 100m, and are installed in clusters connected by seabed cables'. This is misleading, while turbines larger than 15MW exist, the majority deployed are less than this. Additionally, text refers to 2-blade floating turbines; again, these exist as prototypes, but the author needs to check when/if they will be deployed commercially and clarify this in the text.

- Some of the text makes unclear connections.

For example, 'The new wind turbines, where a generator converts mechanical energy into electrical energy, are programmed to achieve maximum efficiency and the lowest possible energy costs. Fluctuating wind energy makes variable speed generators, like permanent magnet (PM) generators, and blades with high strength-to-weight ratios and fatigue resistance, the most suitable options.'

While each element is likely true when considered in isolation, it is unclear what the author tries to say by connecting these points.

- The author has noted potential supply chain constraints and mentions ports in the context of a redevelopment opportunity; the reality is that the lack of port infrastructure and installation vessel availability is likely to create deployment limitations and should be noted and explored as a risk.
- It is unclear if there is an issue with the referencing system or typesetting. Still, many of the references in the footnotes are not complete, and it is difficult to follow the reference from the text to the source, as the numbering system is not chronological.

The examples provided in this review are not an exhaustive list but serve to provide examples.

Please ensure that when revising this manuscript, the text is thoroughly reviewed to ensure that the principles detailed here are applied consistently across the manuscript.

Is the topic of the essay discussed accurately in the context of the current literature?

Partly

Is the work clearly and cogently presented?

Partly

Is the argument persuasive and supported by appropriate evidence?

Partly

Does the essay contribute to the cultural, historical, social understanding of the field?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: offshore wind energy, economic assessment, engineering assessment, resource assessment, financial analysis, policy mapping

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 28 Jun 2025

Marta Avesani

I would like to thank the reviewers for their constructive feedback. In response, the title has been revised to:

"The Mediterranean Offshore Wind Turn: Lessons, Risks, and Regional Reflections"

to more accurately reflect the manuscript's qualitative focus. The manuscript has undergone a thorough review to ensure that all significant claims, including the example highlighted, are now fully supported by appropriate references and evidence. Structural revisions have been made to improve coherence and logical flow between sections, while reducing redundancy, particularly in the discussion of turbine technology. Additionally, illustrative elements have been added where relevant to clarify key interactions and enhance reader understanding. Thank you for the helpful observation regarding the currency of the references.

The relevant sources and data have been carefully reviewed to ensure alignment with the most recent targets and policy frameworks. Outdated references have been replaced with more current sources where appropriate. In instances where earlier references provide important historical context, they have been retained and supplemented with updated data to ensure both accuracy and contextual depth.

The relevant sections have been revised to more clearly distinguish between commercially deployed systems and those that remain at the prototype or demonstration stage. Statements that previously implied widespread commercial availability have been adjusted to reflect the current state of technological development. Specific examples, such as turbine capacity and the status of two-bladed floating turbines, have been clarified to prevent potential misinterpretation.

Revisions have been made to improve the clarity and logical flow of the discussion on turbine design and related technologies. The updated section now more clearly articulates the relationship between energy efficiency, variable-speed generators, and the use of advanced blade materials, ensuring that the connections between these elements are technically accurate and easy to follow.

The discussion has been expanded to address the risks posed by limited port infrastructure and the availability of installation vessels.

These factors are now identified as critical supply chain constraints with potential

implications for deployment timelines and overall project feasibility. The referencing system was significantly disrupted during the typesetting phase. All citations have been carefully reinserted, and the reference list has been reviewed to ensure completeness and correct formatting.

The referencing style has also been converted to an in-text citation format to facilitate easier source tracing. Additionally, new references have been incorporated where necessary to support the revised content and strengthen the overall evidence base.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
